

USING THE PHENOMENON-BASED APPROACH TO TEACH THE SPEECH ACT OF REPROACH

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Abstract: *The training of a competent specialist in any domain is a challenging, long-term process that requires the creation of appropriate conditions for self-acquisition of knowledge and development of professionally significant personality traits. It is obvious that increasing students' autonomous research skills is an important component of the curriculum, which should be paid great attention to and carried out in parallel with the tuition itself. The aim of the article is to examine ways of introducing elements of the Finnish model called the Phenomenon-Based Learning Approach into the curriculum, starting with implementing scenarios of teaching/learning the speech act "reproach".*

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The PhenoBL approach is learner-centred and implemented through a multidisciplinary teaching methodology built on students' curiosity, independent research and activities requiring analytical and investigative skills. This original innovative approach to teaching and learning is based on learners' wish to set goals and “teach themselves” under the supervision of teachers via creative, informative tasks. We come with an activity (lesson plan) intending to show what steps to follow to teach the phenomenon (theme) of reproach within the PhBL frame.

Keywords: 21st century skills, learner-centred, Phenomenon-based learning, problem solving, reproach, speech act, student inquiry, synchronization of education tendencies.

*“Science is beautiful when it makes simple explanations of phenomena or connections between different observations. Examples include the double helix in biology, and the fundamental equations of physics.”
(Stephen Hawking)*

Introduction

Education as a social institution, consciously or intuitively striving to meet the needs and requirements of society, is gradually changing. It is generally acknowledged that the world education system goes through a deep systemic crisis. Even a superficial analysis shows there are several reasons that led to such a state of things. On the one hand it is the COVID 19 restrictions, on the other hand the traditional goals, content, forms and nature of schooling do not correspond to fundamentally new realities of the 21st century any longer. The successful overcoming of the crisis is possible only through the recognition and development of a new educational model, which roots from the reorientation of education towards new contemporary goals. Obviously, no one means cardinal changes in education, as like any social process it is continual, and its parameters change step by step.

We subscribe to M. Karpenko's opinion that “in a modern society, there is an unprecedented demand for higher education” with reference to understanding its crucial importance for the economic and socio-cultural development. A modern society is extremely interested in its citizens' ability to act independently and dynamically, make decisions, adapt flexibly to the changing living conditions. Nowadays, one can observe the tendency of nearly all developed countries to reform their education systems focusing on the students' cognitive activity, i.e. on the process of cognition, and not on teaching. Now higher education opens up new horizons associated with innovative technologies that contribute to the accumulation of new knowledge and its rapid dissemination. The main task is to ensure equal access to such technologies at all levels of the education systems. (Karpenko, 2007: 97). Subsequently, the need of a fundamentally new model of education should be developed and implemented.

Thus, in the modern era of globalization the tendency to change the paradigm of education which could ensure its compliance with the new extremely complex challenges of our dynamic world has become very popular. Therefore, the problem of such a paradigm is widely discussed both in the expert community of academic educators and practitioners. As a result, new educational models have appeared worldwide, besides comparative studies and analysis of foreign experience during periods of crisis and modernization of educational systems, when the search for ways to solve emerging problems have proved to be rather effective. The purpose of considering the foreign experience is the expediency of its practical application in our education system. Moreover, such an approach also corresponds to the modern requirement of synchronization of the national and European education tendencies. Undeniably, the Finnish experience of the Phenomenon-based learning approach is a good example.

Phenomenon-based learning

Being designed and presented by Professor of Educational Psychology at the University of Helsinki Kirsti Lonka, Phenomenon-based learning (PhBL or PhenoBL) has become part of the Finnish national curriculum for all cycles of education, from early to upper secondary education. Its purpose is to make students explore real-life phenomena from different sides. This type of learning is particularly suitable for teaching sciences, but can be applied to all subjects-languages inclusively. This approach focuses on student research, collaboration, and problem solving because the students pick up the content of certain topics, as well as such 21st century skills as teamwork, communication, critical thinking, problem solving and digital literacy. Furthermore, this type of learning allows students to have control over their own learning course through active participation, diversification of learning objectives, approach and types of assessment.

Considering the above-mentioned we can define PhenoBL as an “interdisciplinary approach to learning” in which students are suggested to explore a phenomenon from the real world by means of “asking their own questions, researching facts, and delivering an answer/solution”. The teachers’ role is to monitor the students’ activity during the whole “process, scaffolding the steps and help them through the complexity” (Nielsen & Davies, 2018). To put it differently, the quintessence of the PhenoBL is not just the learning of abstract notions, but studying real life phenomena from a different perspective that gives students the chance to get new knowledge autonomously.

According to Kathy Huncosky, in this context “The word “phenomenon” refers to an observable fact or event occurring in the universe. Most phenomena are not especially flashy or unexpected, but rather are everyday occurrences” (Huncosky, online). In specialised literature more terms describing the same process (i.e., something which takes place in the real surroundings) can be found, for instance *topic, theme, occurrence*.

What is unique for PhenoBL is the fact that no matter what phenomenon (theme) has been picked by the students, it will be studied and regarded from different viewpoints, that is, knowledge of more subjects may be required, thus making it an interdisciplinary approach. Therefore, it is “a pedagogical initiative that [...] has moved away from traditional subject teaching toward multidisciplinary learning modules” (Symeonidis, & Schwarz, 2016: 31-33).

One might ask what stands “behind” this approach to learning and the answer can be found in Stephen Hawking’s statement that “The universe is governed by science. But science tells us that we can’t solve the equations, directly in the abstract. We need to use the effective theory of Darwinian natural selection of those societies most likely to survive. We assign them higher value” (Hawking, apud Sample, 2011).

As specified by Silander (2015 apud Symeonidis& Schwarz) the PhenoBL roots from constructivism and comprises components of “social-cultural learning, progressive inquiry learning and problem-based learning” (Symeonidis& Schwarz, 2016: 37).

In other words, we can explain certain phenomena by means of the knowledge we have obtained from studying other subjects; everything is inter-connected. Thus, learning by PhenoBL makes students use different practices, research, analyse and apply certain crosscutting concepts, and choose the most appropriate disciplinary fundamental ideas to get anticipated results via the “three E”- Exploration, Examination, and Explanation in what manner and why the phenomenon under study occurs.

Nielsen and Davies (2018) also bring evidence in support of using PhenoBL, if not on a regular basis, then at least a couple of times per academic year, claiming that students get involved in researching a phenomenon “because it comes from the real world and it’s relevant to their daily lives”. Students try to clarify how a phenomenon works, regarding it “from multiple

perspectives”, they explore it, “breaking the boundaries of the typical school subjects”. As PhenoBL equals authentic learning, it inspires learners to produce real, valuable “products to be shared with the world”. The researchers summarize their vision of the issue under discussion affirming: “Not only are we, teachers, bringing in real world context to our classrooms, but our students are taking real world issues and problems and developing solutions applicable to the world or community around them” (Nielsen & Davies (2018).

Resulting from K. Taber’s idea that “With the right support, guidance, learning materials or cultural artefacts, learners can achieve tasks that are currently beyond their knowledge but within the zone of proximal development” (Taber, 2011 apud Symeonidis& Schwarz: 38).

Before implementing PhenoBL into practice it is important for teachers to identify what steps to follow and understand how this approach works. Kathy Huncosky, comes with a number of ideas to bear in mind. For instance: (1) to examine the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) performance expectations for the specific level and course; (2) to revise the Disciplinary Core Ideas (DCIs) the learners are anticipated to be familiar with; (3) to brainstorm such phenomena related to the DCIs that might be of interest for learners and can be described by them; (4) to pick out an appropriate “anchor phenomenon” and try to predict a set of questions the learners might come with; (5) to consider the efficacy of the previous lessons and decide whether it is necessary to improve anything or add something new, appropriate in exploring the designated phenomenon; (6) to think over strategies for evaluating students’ knowledge of the chosen phenomenon; (7) to design and systematize probable lesson activities that aim at making learners discover and/or experience the selected phenomenon, involve them in investigative discussions, encouraging them to notice anything interesting about the given phenomenon, share findings and ask questions. At this stage the students are advised to come with diverse ideas as they develop preliminary models while giving details about the phenomenon, making use of prior knowledge of other sciences to try to delve deeper into the phenomenon and improve their descriptions of the phenomenon. The students acquire more data about current scientific concepts that stand behind the phenomenon by doing more activities, such as extended readings, interviewing people, and/or cooperating with experts in the domain, etc. In the process of learning about the phenomenon, they get the chance to go through their reasons and models, creating new ones, etc., later share them and pass to “a class-consensus explanation/model”; and (8) to review the strategy for assessing learners’ comprehension of the studied occurrence, brush it up and complete the assessment (Huncosky, online).

We can highlight the idea that the PhenoBL is getting more and more popular due to its numerous motivational factors. For example, learners feel important as they are directly involved not only in the learning process itself, but also in the planning stage when they all together set specific aims and select the real-world phenomena they would like to explore. They easier understand how these phenomena work in real life and realize their real value. Being learner-centred, the PhenoBL makes students become active initiators and participants in the teaching/ learning process suggesting new original methods and techniques, etc.

The focus of this article is to present elements of the PhenoBL model of teaching the speech act of reproach.

The Speech Act “Reproach”

Modern studies put emphasis on the idea that when considering speech acts (SA) the characteristic features of the communicants, the exact context and situation of the speech interaction should be considered, as well as the fact that the goal of the interaction is not only for the addressee to understand the addresser, but also to evoke in the former a certain reaction to what is heard or done having an impact on it. Thus, the speech act “reproach” is of great interest for research due to its ambiguity and sometimes even difficulty in understanding its real meaning and goal. People use reproaches quite frequently in communication, mainly when they intend to show their disapproval of somebody or something, to i.e., the speaker reacts rather negatively in response to a statement, deed or person.

Reproaches can be described as critical, scornful, depreciating judgments aiming at correcting/ improving something or somebody, with a controlling and adjusting function through the speaker’s influence on the hearer in different contexts. Moreover, in certain situations it can even lead to the emotional anxiety of the listener. It is evident that reproaches are seen as “specific speech acts with a complex intentional content regardless of the context, being considered as a “fusion” of reproach, accusation, and reprimand, which integrate the expression of disapproval and the impact on the addressee’s emotional state” [Varzari, 2020: 16].

From a pragmatic point of view, the addresser’s intention and its correct interpretation by the addressee is significant for the communication to be effective. The students must be aware why it is so vital to take into account the theme of the conversation and the situation in which the process of verbal communication is carried out, as well as the purposes of the communicants.

How to use a reproach properly in communication and not offend the listener still remains challenging in the process of speech interaction. That is why it is necessary to familiarize learners with the structure, semantics, the context and nature of the statements expressing reproach and disapproval. A.O. Ivanov and J. Povey (1989) suggest the following patterns specific for reproach and reprimand.

1. Why (on earth) didn’t you...?
2. You might have.../ I do think you might have... (rather mild)
3. You should have.../ ought to have...
4. You shouldn’t have.../ ought not to have...
5. You ought to be ashamed (of yourself).
6. What do you mean by ...ing? (mixed with anger)
7. You have no right to.... / How dare you...? (very strong, mixed with anger)

The researchers claim that reproach and reprimand are often “used to prevent people, especially children from behaving badly”. For example:

1. What are you up to?
2. Stop (doing) that!
3. Stop fooling around/about!
4. Behave yourself!
5. Be /Act your age!
6. Come on, be a good boy/girl (and...) – (gentle, mild) (Ivanov& Povey, 1989: 64-65).

Applying PhBL in Teaching the Speech Act of Reproach

In order to make the learning process more attractive for students in a modern educational frame, it might be a good idea to make it more ‘democratic’, i.e., to give students the chance to actively participate in the creation of the learning contents suggesting themes and forms that seem appealing to them. In our vision, the PhenoBL approach might be a perfect

model of such type of tuition as it, preserving the content from the curriculum, develops the 21st century skills and gives students the chance to adjust them in conformity with modern trends.

Level: B1-B2

Time: 4-6 hours

Rationale:

It should be noted that the language patterns used to express reproaches are included in the scope of the so-called “etiquette speech formulas” that have become an indispensable part of the speakers’ communicative competence. In order to be a competent language user, the appropriate application into practice of formulas expressing a reproach is obligatory for a well-mannered speaker. Having an important role in people’s communicative and pragmatic competence the SA of reproach is imprinted in the people’s minds as “blame or criticism for something you have done” (Hornby, 2000: 1083).

In various cultures different structures denoting reproach are considered appropriate in agreement with the cultural standards of the given society, disregarding which can be understood as disrespectful. Accordingly, competent speakers must be able to use suitable formulas in specific contexts. Consequently, language teachers should raise their students’ inquisitiveness implicating them into the teaching/learning process via diverse forms and tasks, advocating for investigating a theme, analysing, organizing, working out the results and sharing the results in class.

Procedure:

Step 1. Before announcing the topic of the lesson, the teacher divides the class into several groups (preferably for the students to join a group they like). Each group gets a slip of paper with an extract from stories/ novels containing reproaches. They must read attentively, trying to identify the theme (phenomenon) described in the passage, then share with other groups and decide together. If necessary, the teacher tries to elicit the main theme (in our case *reproach*) by asking leading in questions.

Step 2. The students and teachers decide on the goals, schedule and deadlines.

Step 3. Orientation/ background knowledge. Students watch a video¹²³ about reproaches and at the end they will have a free discussion to share their thoughts. The discussion continues in pairs/groups (depending on the number of students and timeframe). The idea is that each student helps their pair/group to learn by discussing, revising and testing each other. At the end of the discussion, they make graphic representations of the data designing a poster, leaflet, etc. to summarize their ideas.

Step 4. Getting acquainted with the posters. Each pair/group pins their posters on the walls and then walk around the classroom in pairs/groups, look at all the posters and discuss the topic with their partner(s). The teacher helps the students, if necessary, to actively process the topic by prompting or hinting.

Step 5. Practicing. The teacher helps the students to evaluate their knowledge in a critical way. The students stand in front of their own posters and reflect on what they know about the topic, what they do not know yet, and what they should know.

Step 6. Distributing responsibilities. Having acknowledged the phenomenon to be explored (the speech act of reproach) the students are encouraged to decide how exactly they are going to solve the set goals, i.e., what procedures and tools are to be involved.

¹²³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kqW_ypKtFh4

Step 7. Gaining new knowledge. The teacher guides the students explaining them where and how to look for appropriate data¹²⁴. The students can search for information on the Internet in pairs/groups trying to find answers to the questions from the previous stage, (1) what they do not know about the subject yet and (2) what they should know. Learners are encouraged to meet and consult experts in the field such as librarians, teachers of other subjects, native speakers to learn about reproaching models appropriate for different cultures, etc.

Step 8. Delving deeper. Having enriched their knowledge by reading and stocking new information they might identify problems to be solved. Students reflect in groups/pairs on the new knowledge: what they learned about the phenomenon, how their knowledge developed and what new questions arose. Students write short notes about these findings, completing their portfolio for further consultation.

Step 9. Preparing the presentation of the project. At this stage the learners systematize the gained information and think over the form of their presentation (video, poster, PowerPoint, article, etc.). If necessary, they ask for the teacher's guidance.

Step 10. Presenting the project. Each pair/group shares with their group mates the results of their joint efforts- their final product. Questions are encouraged, and in case the students have got difficulties answering them, the answers are found together through discussion.

Step 11. Evaluating the project. As within the PhBL approach learners are stimulated to self-evaluate their own results and get feedback from their peers; it teaches students to be self-critical, as well as accurate, correct and objective while evaluating others. This type of assessment has got several advantages: from being impartial towards oneself and others to improving the communicative and pragmatic competences.

Conclusion

The world is changing very rapidly today, as well as people's priorities, living conditions, goals and values. Under these circumstances, the scenarios of training the younger generations for a fruitful life and career success gets much more complex. Unfortunately, our educational systems fail to quickly adjust to new changes that may lead to a discrepancy between the content and nature of traditional education and the new realities of the near future. Thus, life itself requires the urgent development of a fundamentally new educational paradigm, that will meet the criteria of the new 21st century society.

We are firmly convinced that the PhenoBL model is an example how to modernize the teaching/learning process making the students be in charge for their own learning while searching for an answer to a creative research problem. It develops in the young generation the skills which are indispensable in the modern world. The students become effective team members, improve their communicative and pragmatic skills, enhance their creativity and get better critical thinking abilities. The students learn how to use the knowledge they have into practice, which makes learning more appealing. They get the chance to study independently about the speech act of reproach in several languages, its structural patterns and how it is appropriately used in speech.

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